

STUDIES IN THE CAMPHOR SERIES. PART IV.
SYNTHESIS OF THIOFENCHONE AND TWO
ISOMERIC BIS-THIOCAMPHORS AND
THEIR DERIVATIVES.

BY DINES CHANDRA SEN.

Thiofenchone, previously prepared by Rimini (*Gazzetta*, 1909, **39**, 203), has been obtained as a deep red liquid by the simultaneous action of dry hydrogen chloride and sulphuretted hydrogen at 0° on freshly distilled fenchone in alcoholic solution. Like a ketone it gives with evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen a semicarbazone and an oxime which are found to be identical with those of fenchone. On reduction with aluminium amalgam, it gives thiofenchol. It forms also a white crystalline mercury salt with mercuric acetate. It decolourises iodine and permanganate solutions and also forms a yellow silver salt. All these properties lead to the following constitutional formulæ of thiofenchone and thiofenchol:

The reactive nature of the methylene group due to the negative influence of a thiocarbonyl group (*cf.* Sen, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 751; 1936, **13**, 523; *Nature*, 1936, **138**, 548) has made it possible to synthesise two isomeric bis-thiocamphors by the action of iodine on the sodio derivative of thiocamphor in boiling benzene. Bis-thiocamphor can be represented by either (I) or (II).

Oddo's method (*cf.* *Gazzetta*, 1897, **27**, 149; 1911, **41**, 126; *Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 1569) of synthesis of bis-camphor, namely by the action of sodium

or magnesium on α -bromocamphor cannot be applied for the synthesis of bis-thiocamphor, as α -bromothiocamphor cannot be prepared in the pure state. The action of iodine on sodio-camphor in benzene on the other hand gives α -iodocamphor instead of bis-camphor.

dl-Bis-thiocamphor (m.p. 164°) forms a dioxime, (m.p. 199° , decomp.) and an azine (m.p. 176°), and *l*-bis-thiocamphor (m.p. 180°) also forms an azine (m.p. 200°) under similar conditions. These facts, along with the analytical and molecular weight data of the two bis-thiocamphors and their derivatives lead to the conclusion that they contain two C:S groups, and that they are 1:4-dithioketones, and have the formula (II). The dioximes and the azines should, therefore, be represented by the structures (III) and (IV) respectively.

On reduction with aluminium amalgam in moist ethereal solution, *dl*-bis-thiocamphor forms *dl*-bis-thioborneol, m.p. 148° , which decolourises iodine and forms a yellow lead salt.

l-Bis-thiocamphor has a very high molecular rotation, $[\text{M}]_D^{30} = -1109.5$ in benzene solution, whereas the molecular rotation of *l*-thiocamphor is $[\text{M}]_D^{30} = -41.3$ in the same solvent and under similar conditions. This high exaltation in optical activity may be attributed to the presence of a potential conjugated system in bis-thiocamphor, which may behave both in the thio and thiol phases.

Studies in absorption spectra in the visible region of bis-thiocamphor at different dilutions and the comparison of these with those of thiofenchone and thiocamphor have given interesting results. It has been noticed that a 5.4% solution of bis-thiocamphor in benzene manifests a characteristic absorption band between $5270\text{\AA}$ and $4530\text{\AA}$ and that with dilution this

band becomes shorter corresponding to dilutions 4.5% and 3.6%. Finally at 2.7% concentration it gives a very short band having the centre at $4950\text{\AA}$. Similar bands have also been observed in the case of *l*-thiocamphor and *d*-thiofenchone. This selective absorption band is, therefore, a characteristic property of the chromophoric C:S group in cyclic thioketones.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Thiofenchone.—A simultaneous current of hydrogen chloride and sulphuretted hydrogen was passed for 6 hours into an alcoholic solution of freshly distilled fenchone (50 g.). The product was poured into water and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried over sodium sulphate, ether removed and the residual liquid distilled in vacuum. On repeated fractionation, thiofenchone distilled at $92^\circ/5$ mm. ($215\text{--}16^\circ/762$ mm.) as a red liquid having camphoric smell, yield 5 g. [Found: C, 71.21; H, 9.63; S, 19.12; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 167. Calc. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{S}$: C, 71.43; H, 9.52; S, 19.05 per cent. M.W., 168]. The *oxime* was prepared by the action of hydroxylamine hydrochloride in pyridine solution, m.p. 159° . (Found: N, 8.35. Calc. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{17}\text{ON}$: N, 8.38 per cent). The *semicarbazone* was prepared by the action of semicarbazide hydrochloride on thiofenchone in alcoholic solution, m.p. 172° . (Found: N, 20.15. Calc. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{19}\text{ON}_3$: N, 20.09 per cent). These derivatives have been found to be identical with fenchone oxime and fenchone semicarbazone.

Reduction of Thiofenchone.—Thiofenchone was reduced by aluminium amalgam in a similar manner as described in the case of thiocamphor (*cf.* Sen, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 647) in moist ethereal solution. The ethereal solution was evaporated and the residue treated with a concentrated solution of lead acetate (lead salt of thiofenchol being fairly soluble in alcohol, the solution of lead salt should be very concentrated). The precipitated lead salt was filtered off, suspended in alcohol and decomposed by means of sulphuretted hydrogen. The oil was precipitated from the alcoholic solution and extracted with ether, dried over sodium sulphate, ether evaporated and the liquid distilled at $95^\circ/5$ mm. or at $216\text{--}220^\circ/762$ mm. It was obtained as a *colourless* liquid having a smell similar to that of thioborneol. (Found: C, 70.68; H, 10.75; S, 18.91. Calc. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{18}\text{S}$: C, 70.59; H, 10.59; S, 18.82 per cent). Thiofenchol decolourises bromine and iodine solutions and also dilute potassium permanganate solution in the cold.

l-Bis-thiocamphor.—A solution of dry *l*-thiocamphor (20 g.) in sodium-dried benzene (50 c. c.) was treated with powdered sodamide (4.8 g.) and the solution boiled for nearly 1 hour under reflux, till the red colour of

thiocamphor completely vanished. A solution of iodine (15 g.) in benzene was then added drop by drop to the boiling solution. The boiling was continued for half an hour more and the solution treated with ice-cold water. The benzene solution was washed with water and sodium thiosulphate solution, dried over sodium sulphate and the benzene distilled. The viscous liquid solidified on stirring and it was washed with alcohol which removed the tarry matter. The residual solid on crystallisation from alcohol gave orange hexagonal plates, m. p. 180° , yield 6 g.

It is moderately soluble in alcohol and readily soluble in benzene giving a deep red solution. It has the normal molecular weight and is *laevo*-rotatory, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -332^{\circ}$ in 1 per cent. solution in benzene observed in a 2 dcm. tube. [Found : C, 71'81; H, 9'12; S, 19'26. M. W. (in benzene, cryoscopic), 332. $C_{20}H_{30}S_2$ requires C, 71'86; H, 8'98; S, 19'16 per cent. M. W., 336].

The *dioxime* was prepared by heating *l*-bis-thiocamphor (1 g.) in pyridine (5 c. c.) with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1 g.). The solution was heated at 100° for 1 hour till the evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen was complete and the solution became colourless. It was then poured into water (500 c. c.) and the white precipitate crystallised from alcohol as needles, m.p. 197° , yield 0.6 g. (Found : C, 71'95; H, 9'84; N, 8'38 per cent. $C_{20}H_{32}O_2N_2$ requires C, 72'2; H, 9'64; N, 8'43 per cent).

Dicamphane Azine.—A solution of *l*-bis-thiocamphor (2 g.) in alcohol (4 c. c.) was treated with hydrazine hydrate (3 c. c.) in the cold. The formation of azine was accompanied with evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen and the disappearance of the red colour. The solution was poured into water and the precipitate crystallised from alcohol as shining needles, m.p. 200° (decomp.), yield 1.5 g. (Found : C, 79'75; H, 9'89; N, 9'34. $C_{20}H_{30}N_2$ requires C, 79'47; H, 9'93; N, 9'27 per cent). It is soluble in all organic solvents and mineral acids. The *picrate* was obtained as yellow shining needles, m. p. 200° (decomp.). (Found : N, 13'35. $C_{26}H_{33}O_7N_5$ requires N, 13'28 per cent).

dl-Bis-thiocamphor.—It was prepared in the same manner as *l*-bis-thiocamphor, m. p. 164° . (Found : C, 71'85; H, 9'21; S, 19'22. M. W., 332. $C_{20}H_{30}S_2$ requires C, 71'86; H, 8'98; S, 19'16 per cent. M. W., 336). The *dioxime* crystallises from alcohol as needles, m. p. 199° (decomp.). (Found : C, 72'25; H, 9'65; N, 8'45. $C_{20}H_{32}O_2N_2$ requires C, 72'2; H, 9'64; N, 8'43 per cent). The corresponding *diazine*, prepared by the action of hydrazine hydrate on the alcoholic solution of *dl*-bis-thiocamphor melts at 176° . (Found : C, 79'53; H, 10'03; N, 9'35. $C_{20}H_{30}N_2$ requires C, 79'47; H, 9'93; N, 9'27 per cent).

Reduction of dl-bis-thiocamphor: Preparation of dl-bis-thioborneol.— Aluminium amalgam was added in the cold to the moist ethereal solution of *dl*-bis-thiocamphor (10 g.). The solution was kept for 2 days when reduction was complete, as was evident from the disappearance of the red colour. The solution was filtered off and concentrated after drying over sodium sulphate. It crystallised from alcohol as colourless needles having a characteristic smell like that of thioborneol, m. p. 143° , yield 7 g. (Found : C, 71.25 ; H, 10.19 ; S, 19.02. M. W. 338. $C_{20}H_{34}S_2$ requires C, 71.0 ; H, 10.06 ; S, 18.94 per cent. M. W., 338).

Determination of Absorption Spectra in the Visible Regions.

The absorption spectra of *l*-thiocamphor, *l*-bis-thiocamphor and thiofenchone in benzene were determined in quartz cell of thickness 0.5 cm. and the variations of the bands with dilutions are shown in the accompanying plate. Spectra corresponding to the following dilutions were compared, (1) 5.4%, (2) 4.5%, (3) 3.6%, (4) 2.7%, and it was noticed that at 5.4% concentration all the substances gave an absorption band between 5270Å — 4530Å having the band centre at 4950Å , corresponding to dilution of 2.7 per cent.

My thanks are due to Sir P. C. Rây for his kind encouragement during the investigation and also for the facilities in his laboratory.